

Research Article

The Factors Affecting the Implementation of The Municipal Council of Windhoek's 2017-2022 Transformational Strategic Plan in Namibia

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Abstract	Manuscript Information
<p>This study aimed to assess the effectiveness of the transformational strategic plan for the period: 2017-2022 and identify implementation challenges faced by the Municipal Council of Windhoek. The study depended on self-administered questionnaires distributed to Municipal Council of Windhoek employees to collect data. The effect of; strategic formulation, council and senior management leadership, organizational culture, organizational design, resources, communication, and incentives, on implementing the Municipal Council of Windhoek 2017 - 2022 transformational strategic plan was evaluated using a quantitative data analysis approach using descriptive statistics. Furthermore, challenges affecting strategic plan implementation were identified using a thematic qualitative data analysis approach. The results indicated that the effect of all considered factors was of high importance to implementing the strategic plan. Furthermore, results indicated that apart from incentives, which had a low effect; the remaining six factors had a moderate effect on the implementation of the Municipal Council of Windhoek 2017 - 2022 transformational strategic plan. In addition, results indicated that the implementation of the 2017 – 2022 strategic plan for the Municipal Council of Windhoek faced several challenges with lack of funds and leadership vacuum being the most common shared challenges by respondents. Conversely, financial resources and support of the council and senior management leadership were the most commonly identified factors that contributed to the successful implementation of the Municipal Council of Windhoek 2017 – 2022 strategic plan. Following the study's findings, The Municipal Council of Windhoek should improve its financial resources for all projects and activities in the strategic plan. Furthermore, there is a need for the Municipal Council of Windhoek to implement the performance management system in order to improve the accountability of employees.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ ISSN No: 2583-7397 ▪ Received: 13-08-2024 ▪ Accepted: 25-09-2024 ▪ Published: 24-11-2024 ▪ IJCRM:3(6); 2024: 48-65 ▪ ©2024, All Rights Reserved ▪ Plagiarism Checked: Yes ▪ Peer Review Process: Yes <p>How to Cite this Manuscript</p> <p>Queen Omagano Kamati, Nikodemus Angula. Investigating The Factors Affecting the Implementation of The Municipal Council of Windhoek's 2017-2022 Transformational Strategic Plan in Namibia. International Journal of Contemporary Research in Multidisciplinary.2024; 3(6):48-65.</p>

KEYWORDS: Strategic planning process, Stakeholder engagement, Performance indicators, Monitoring and evaluation, Resource allocation, Capacity building.

1. INTRODUCTION

Strategic planning refers to the management process in which organizations set goals and objectives to achieve stable and anticipated growth of the organization (Maleka, 2014). Part of the process is determining the order in which those goals should be accomplished so that the organization can achieve its stated vision (Bigelow, 2022). Therefore, the execution of a strategic plan entails carrying out one or more of the strategies outlined in the plan. However, during the implementation process, certain challenges arise that prevent obtaining the planned results in the projected time frame, resulting in overruns of the assigned resources and worst of all, failure to achieve the planned objectives despite all efforts and expenses. Usually, these challenges are not presented directly, but their existence could be observed through the manifestations and negative consequences, which they cause (Rojas-Acre, 2012).

Mutie (2014) assessed factors that are crucial for successful implementation of strategic plans in some churches in Kenya. According to the findings, as the need for strategic planning grows, companies are realizing that strategic planning allows them to be competitive and adapt to changing market dynamics. In South Africa, the Department of Environmental Affairs and Development Planning (DEA&DP) creates a five-year national strategic plan for municipalities. This is in accordance with the country's constitution, which mandates DEA&DP to promote developmental local government, establish municipalities in accordance with national legislation, and regulate municipal performance (Department of Local Government, 2020). In South Africa, strategic planning implementation faces a number of challenges, including disparity in infrastructure planning and management between the three organs of the government; aging infrastructure and a lack of regular maintenance; and economics shortcomings, which leads to reduced distributions of funds from the National and Provincial Governments to support capital economic stimulus (Department of Local Government, 2020).

According to a Czech Republic study on how to improve strategic planning of municipal organizations, the majority of strategic plans did not fulfill the requirements for strategic management tools needed to effectively contribute to the future growth of municipalities (Řehoř, 2015). This indicates that although there are policies in place for implementation of strategic planning remains a challenge in some part of the world. The success of any strategic plan is dependent on the ability to actualize the formulated strategy thus promoting the need to ensure that the formulated strategy is successfully implemented (Mutie, 2014).

1.1 Background of the study

As the nation's capital and economic hub, the Municipal Council of Windhoek (Municipal Council of Windhoek) plays a unique role in Namibia's broad-based social and economic development trajectory. As a result, the city bears a substantial amount of responsibility towards national-building and setting patterns for other local governments around the country. Windhoek is the largest city in Namibia with a population of about 325,858 people by the year 2011 (Namibia Statistics Agency, 2011).

Furthermore, the Municipal Council of Windhoek welcomed its position in aiding Namibia in accomplishing its developmental goals as outlined in Vision 2030 and National Development Plans (National Planning Commission, 2013). According to former Windhoek Mayor Muesee Kazapua, the strategic plan is paired with a yearly budget cycle, allowing the organization to match strategic objectives and resources needed (City of Windhoek, 2017). Furthermore, the City of Windhoek's strategic plan is unique in that it is coupled with an annual budget cycle, allowing the organization to align the strategic projects and resource needed (City of Windhoek, 2017).

In terms of service delivery, local governments are the closest to the people. It provides services such as the supply of water and electricity, sewerage services, road maintenance, servicing of land, sale, and lease of land other services as set out by the local authority's amendment act (Act No. 17 of 2002) (OPM, 2002). To carry out this effectively, local governments must have a solid organizational strategy. Municipalities and village councils in Namibia, like elsewhere in the world, play an important role in ensuring access to basic services while meeting resident and stakeholder expectations within the constraints of available resources. There are three different types of local governments in Namibia: municipal (city) councils, town councils, and village councils. In total, these local governments are 57 across the country and all of them have their strategic plans.

Windhoek's Municipal Council has been working to establish a strong and accountable governance structure. The Transformational Plan (TP) 2017-2022 strategy was initiated in September 2016 in collaboration with the Khomas Regional Council and other stakeholders after the Integrated Business Plan (IBP: 2011-2016) came to an end. Furthermore, the first two years of the IBP: 2011-2016 laid the foundation for a successful turnaround approach, including clear governance, financial rescue, and strategic funding strategies. As a result, the Municipal Council of Windhoek have improved in some important performance areas, such as achieving clean annual audit (City of Windhoek, 2017).

The City of Windhoek's transformational plan for the period 2017-2022 focused on two distinct themes: "financial sustainability and governance" as well as "social progression, economic advancement, and infrastructure development." These themes sought to ensure that the Municipal Council of Windhoek is well-governed and financially sound, while also strengthening organizational strength and ability. Furthermore, the themes enabled Municipal Council of Windhoek to be more effective by providing access to urban amenities, socioeconomic opportunities, geographical inclusivity, high-quality urban environments, and a vibrant city life (City of Windhoek, 2017). Given the increasing emphasis on socio-economic upliftment, lessons learnt from the previous strategic period imply the need to prioritize this issue in collaboration with significant stakeholders. Furthermore, any strategic plan's success depends on its ability to actualize the defined strategy, hence it is important to make sure that it is successfully implemented (Mutie, 2014). Therefore, an assessment of the transformational plan's implementation process for the period 2017-2022 is

required, with a focus on the implementation challenges encountered, to inform decisions on the development of the subsequent strategic plan for the next five years (2023 – 2028). Consequently, the goal of this study was to evaluate these challenges to determine how they affected the implementation of the transformational plan for the period 2017-2022.

1.2 Statement of the problem

Challenges to successful strategic plan implementation have been reported worldwide in various sectors, including municipalities (Rojas-Acre, 2012; Mutie, 2014; Řehoř, 2015). In Namibia, several challenges have been identified in the implementation of the City of Windhoek's strategic plans Vries (2014). The Municipal Council of Windhoek's (Municipal Council of Windhoek) transformational strategic plan for the period 2017-2022 is the primary strategic framework that drives decision-making within the organization and aids in directing the city's efforts on core business and budget targets (City of Windhoek, 2017). Furthermore, the City of Windhoek transformational strategic plan for 2017-2022 was aimed at accelerating the organizational performance and improving service delivery to the residents of Windhoek (City of Windhoek, 2017).

In many cases, studies on strategic planning for various institutions and organizations regarded strategic plans as a fixed routine with a focus on determining whether a set of procedures was followed (George, *et al.*, 2016). However, following as set of procedures does not guarantee successful implementation of strategic plans. Thus, a holistic approach in the development and implementation of strategic plans needs to be considered. This can be achieved by conducting in-depth studies that allow the identification of challenges in order to inform future strategies. The City of Windhoek transformational strategic plans will be lapsed in 2022 and the new strategic plan for the next five years should be in the process of being developed. Therefore, it is necessary to assess whether the current strategic plan was successful in light of the resources spent on its development and implementation. However, there is little indication of a thorough analysis of the City of Windhoek's transformative strategic plan's (2017–2022) implementation. This results in a lack of considerable insights into how to make future strategic plans more successful (Poister 2010). Therefore, this study will fill the gap in the knowledge on the effectiveness of the City of Windhoek's transformational strategic plan for the period from 2017 to 2022 and identify challenges faced during the implementation of the current strategic plans. This is important in providing informed guidelines for the implementation of future strategies.

1.3 Purpose of the Study

The main objective of this study was to assess the effectiveness of the transformational strategic plan for the period: 2017-2022 and identify implementation challenges faced by the Municipal Council of Windhoek.

1.3.1 RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The specific objectives of the study were to:

1. Evaluate how the Municipal Council of Windhoek implemented its transformational strategic plan (2017-2022).
2. Identify the challenges that affected the implementation of the transformational strategic plan (2017-2022) for the Municipal Council of Windhoek.
3. Examine and outline the critical success factors of the strategic plan implementation.

To recommend potential mechanisms for improving the Windhoek Municipal Council's strategic plan implementation.

1.3.2 Research Questions

1. How was the Transformational Strategic Plan 2017-2022 of the Municipal Council of Windhoek implemented?
2. What are the challenges that affected the successful implementation of the transformational strategic plan (2017-2022) for the Municipal Council of Windhoek?
3. What are the drivers for the successful implementation of a strategic plan?
4. How can the implementation and evaluation of the new strategic plan be improved?

1.4 Significance of the Study

Studies have shown that good organizational performance depends on the strategic plans' successful implementation. (George, 2021). In terms of local authorities, particularly the City of Windhoek, the findings of this study provided valuable information on the challenges that municipalities face, as well as potential mitigating factors for improved implementation of future strategic plans. Furthermore, the findings can also help to shape future government policies that govern local authorities in the country, particularly future amendments to the Local Authority Act. The findings have also added to the established body of scientific knowledge, which will benefit scholars working on topics related to the implementation of strategic plans in local governments. Moreover, the findings are expected to benefit local universities by providing lecturers and students with up-to-date information on the topic.

1.5 Limitations of the Study

This study only focused on the success and challenges of implementing one strategic plan for the City of Windhoek, and the findings cannot be generalized to compare with studies that covered multiple municipalities. Findings from this study may also not be comparable to other local authorities in the country due to the size of the monetary budget for the City of Windhoek. The study sample of the City of Windhoek population was limited by the employees' willingness to participate in the survey. The questionnaire method of data collection also limited the data to personal opinions and assumptions, which could differ if raw quantitative data was collected to answer the research questions. Furthermore, more sensitive information such as financial and other confidential matters has not been disclosed.

1.6 Delimitations of the study

The study only focused on some employees of Municipal Council of Windhoek, to collect data. Thus, this study only considered factors affecting the implementation the City of Windhoek strategic plan for a period of five years (2017- 2022).

1.7 Chapter summary

This chapter examined the study's problem statement, background information that clarifies the brief history of the strategy implementation plan, and study introduction. The research goals that serve as a researcher's road map are described in the chapter. Additionally, it outlines the current study's importance, constraints, and boundaries.

2. Literature review and research hypotheses

2.1 Concept of strategy

A strategy is a plan of action that will help an organization achieve its goals. To help a company achieve corporate success, there is a broad program of objectives and initiatives (Porter, 2012). Mintzberg (2014) asserts that the five P's can be used to define strategy, which are plan, ploy, position, pattern, and perspective. When taken as a viewpoint, strategy explicitly refers to a technique of situating an organization in a context. This makes it the mediating force on how to preserve a fit or match between the internal and external environment of the organization.

2.2 Strategic planning

The definition of strategic planning is "a systematic endeavour to develop basic decisions and activities that form and guide an organization's identity, mission, and goals" (Bryson 2012). It offers a methodical approach for compiling data on the large picture, using it to determine a long-term course of action, and then converting that course of action into precise goals, targets, and actions. In order to map out a future plan of action that will guarantee the organization's long-term life and performance, it combines futuristic thinking, objective analysis, and subjective appraisal of goals and priorities. At its best, it encompasses an organization's culture and creates a sense of direction and importance that is almost obvious (Osborne & Gaebler 2012). According to Mintzberg *et al.*, (1988) a component of this process also involves the creation of benchmarks that will allow the organization to determine how well it is performing against goals and objectives as it implements the strategic plan. The strategic planning committee works by conducting research and compiling the data necessary to comprehend both the organization's current situation and the elements that will have an impact on it in the future (Daniel, 2019). Strategic planning offers several advantages since it makes organizations more aware of potential possibilities and difficulties in the future. Additionally, it forces organizations to recognize the resources that will be required to take advantage of or overcome such chances and obstacles. Strategic planning also helps organize people around a single goal and provides them a feeling of direction. It establishes responsibility and norms. Organizations that use strategic planning can also reduce or eliminate the

amount of time they spend responding to unforeseen changes that they did not foresee or prepare for. Many sizable businesses adopted a standardized top-down strategic planning strategy in the 1970s.

2.3 Strategic implementation

Strategy implementation is a collection of the necessary procedures and actions that an organization must do in order to implement its strategic plan (Jooste and Fourie 2009). According to Mintzberg (2004), an effective execution of a strategic plan depends on the environment for learning and growth among employees, who serve as the real implementers. Learning places, a strong emphasis on transparency, teamwork, equity, trust, ongoing development, and taking risks. Guth and McMillan (1986) noted that managerial involvement was crucial for organizations to achieve the targeted implementation and that it boosted success in implementing strategy when middle level managers were involved.

The most significant management difficulty currently facing all types of organizations is the implementation of strategies, according to the White Paper of Strategy Implementation of Chinese Corporations from 2006 (Mumbua & Mingaine 2015). According to the poll mentioned in the white paper, only 17 percent of the surveyed organizations believed they had a consistent strategy implementation procedure, and 83 percent of the companies failed to implement their strategies smoothly. It follows that strategy implementation is unquestionably a significant challenge for service organizations. There are several factors that influence the success of strategy implementation, encompassing both the individuals who convey or carry out the strategy as well as the systems or controls in place. Even the best-designed strategies will face failure if they are not carried out correctly. The implementation of a strategy cannot take place, according to Guth (1986), unless there is stability between the strategy and every aspect of the company, including its organizational structure, compensation system, and resource-allocation procedure.

2.3 Factors affecting implementation

Ricky (2012) identified structure, people resources, leadership, culture, information systems, and technology as key implementation variables (Fig. 1).

Figure 2.1 Factors Affecting Implementation of strategies
(Source: Daniel, 2019).

2.3.1 Organizational Structure

Organizational culture is described by Kennedy (2000) as the underlying presumptions, values, and modes of interaction that contribute to the distinctive social and psychological environment of an organization. Members' self-perceptions, internal workings, interactions with the outside world, and expectations for the future are manifestations of organizational culture because they contain an organization's goals, experiences, philosophies, and the principles that guide its members' behaviour (Needle, 2004). Strong organizational culture is a set of firm principles that all employees uphold and that centers recruitment on culture fit rather than just skill set, allowing for greater individual autonomy while maintaining what is most important for the company (Daniel, 2019).

According to Hill and Jones (2013), an organization's culture has a direct or indirect impact on its efficiency and effectiveness, which is why it is important to have a culture that values dedication, efficiency, effectiveness, and openness. According to Kennedy (2000), incentives have a significant impact on culture. By incentives, we refer to the complete range of rewards, including monetary rewards, non-monetary benefits like status, recognition, and advancement, and sanctions that members of the organization are subject to.

According to Arabi (2012), executing a strategy is a process in which all planning and budgeting initiatives, as well as policies and practices, adhere to the established strategy. It could entail minor adjustments to an organization's culture, structure, and management system, or perhaps a significant overall shift in every one of the aforementioned areas. Unless a broad range of adjustments were absolutely necessary for the organization, middle managers particularly execute the strategy after top managers provide their approval. The daily decisions made on resource allocation fall under the umbrella of strategy implementation, often known as "operational planning." According to Daft (2013), some direct consequences of an

organization's fundamental structure may have an effect on its first operational structure. Additionally, general fundamental policies can affect an organization's evolved operational level. Similar to this, choosing a certain design's intended use—such as divisional—will frequently result in a different design of that same kind (functional design). The following factors should be considered in order to establish an adaptive and conforming relationship between structure and strategy: assessing the structure's level of adaptability, centralization and decentralization, the relationship between strategy and structure, correlating to gain and share information throughout the organization, and lastly, defining roles.

2.3.2 Resource Allocation

Resource allocation is a strategy for utilizing available resources to accomplish specific objectives. Both financial and human resources are included in this (Daniel, 2019). Effective resource allocation is hampered by a number of issues, such as excessive resource protection, an overemphasis on short-term financial objectives, organizational politics, ambiguous strategy aims, an unwillingness to take risks, and a lack of information. It goes both ways when it comes to resources and strategy.

2.3.3 Human resource

Porter (2012) asserts that managers need strong interpersonal and human abilities in order to implement plans successfully. Both management and staff are impacted by all activities taken to implement the strategy. How to effectively implement an organization's strategies is a question that each division of a firm tries to address. Implementing strategies is also a part of practical strategic management. The objective of putting strategies into action is for management and personnel to collaborate in order to carry out developed strategic planning. The success of implementation depends on managers' capacity to motivate employees.

2.3.4 Leadership

Today, a strategic planner's role is to properly steer the organization so that it can benefit from growth opportunities. In reality, they have a big impact on fostering character development and economic success. Lehner (2014) identifies their main objectives as employee motivation and skill development. If strategy is a decision, then creating opportunities for people to participate successfully should not be a manager's primary concern in terms of other responsibilities.

2.3.5 Information systems and implementation of strategy

The role of information systems in process implementation focuses mostly on internal information exchange and manifests on environmental uncertainty problem. Managers' requirement for reciprocal information exchange is another significant issue that highlights the relevance of information systems in putting strategy into practice (Mumbua & Mingaine 2015). It speaks of an apparatus that disseminates info both upward and downward. The management information system is a tool that managers can use to compile and arrange data for their tasks. According to the

strategic management process, planning and execution are separated in terms of information relevance while information fluency and impacting directions regularly reciprocate. All components should be self-sufficient and well matched to the capabilities of information systems, and software and hardware should provide global interoperability, to name a few recommendations for increasing the effectiveness of information systems in implementing plans (a sort of stable procedure for the entire world).

2.4 Conceptual models and frameworks for strategy implementation

Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats (SWOT) analysis, Porter's generic strategies, and portfolio models are a few of the commonly used models and frameworks that are available to researchers and practitioners in the fields of strategy analysis, formulation, and implementation in strategic management (Okumus, 2003 & Wheelan and Hunger, 2012). Contrarily, there is not a recognized, widely used, or dominating framework for implementing strategies (Abdulrahman, 2019). Hourani (2017) recognized eight (8) of the most significant conceptual models or adaptations of approaches in strategy implementation currently used by both academics and practitioners after examining literature that made major contributions to conceptual models and frameworks (Approaches). According to Hourani (2017), these methodologies (models and frameworks) can be broadly divided into two (2) classes. Factor-oriented approach: The first category viewed the execution of the strategy as the sum of all the individual components that interact, interact, and integrate with the implementation of the strategy. The next category is a process-oriented approach that emphasizes strategic change, the need for strategic continuity, intentionality and rational structuring versus the emergence of strategy, as well as issues with organizational buy-in, management leadership, providing the necessary culture, and communicating strategy to the organization (Dameron & Torset (2014), Li *et al.*, 2008). Both of the discussed techniques, according to Okumus (2003), are based on distinct factors with distinct interrelationships between the various variables. Any study's conceptual framework is a hypothesis presented as a diagram that aims to link and depict the relationships between the variables being studied (Mugenda & Mugenda, 2003). It is assumed that the efficient components account for variation in strategy execution (the dependent variable) (independent variables). The process of putting a strategy into action should be reviewed, as should the ideas surrounding it, including organizational structure, leadership, human resources, technology, and information control systems. It will be important to work as a team, have motivated and trained personnel, employ modern technology to save costs, and have proper channels for information exchange in order to successfully implement a strategy.

Figure 2.2: Conceptual Framework

2.5 Empirical Analysis of Different Studies

In order to better understand the elements that help and impede the implementation of strategic plans, numerous researches were carried out globally. Studies primarily focus on the connection between organizational performance in Kenya and the implementation of strategic plans. In Non-Governmental Organizations, factors affecting the successful implementation of strategic plans were examined by Abok *et al.*, (2013). The national cereals and produce board were the subject of a research Daniel (2019), on the factors influencing strategy implementation in government parastatals. Numerous researches have been done on the variables influencing strategic plan execution in public sectors. According to research by Salum *et al.*, (2017), among the reasons why public organizations struggle to implement strategic plans is the issue with poor strategic plan design. Poor resource management and monitoring and assessment are further contributing issues. The failure of leaders to manage and inspire their teams to achieve the goals of the strategic plan is criticized.

Yang *et al.*, (2010) research showed that the involvement and interventions of an organization's highest level of management foster greater commitment levels in the implementation of a firm's vision and strategies, which in turn fosters success in the implementation of a firm's chosen strategy. Smith and Kofron (1996), however, thought that the senior management played a significant role not only in the formulation but also in the implementation of the strategy. Masuku & Jili (2019) states that in order for African governments to use local authorities as tools to carry out developmental goals, local authorities had to be pressured to adopt incentives that were modelled after NPM policies like strategic management, which favoured the creation and execution of strategic plans. Wright & Davis (2003) claimed that an organization's orientation is determined by the strategies it plans for a year or more. Therefore, the entire organization needs to be involved for an organization to be able to achieve its specified strategic objectives. As stated by Noble (1999), "organizations may have formulated the best strategies, but the strategies may fail to achieve the expected results if they are not implemented in the appropriate way," strategic plans may not yield the anticipated results. Alexander (1985) found that one of the most commonly cited factors that contributed to the successful implementation of a strategy was communication. Therefore, effective communication should clearly outline the new roles, obligations, and activities that the targeted staff must

do. According to Chimanzi and Morgan's (2005) study, businesses that prioritize marketing and employee engagement get higher percentages of plan execution. Therefore, Chimanzi and Morgan (2005) suggested that managers in charge of marketing should concentrate on strengthening connections with their counterparts (human resource) by supporting written communication and collaborative reward systems, thereby emphasizing a two-way process-based dimension. Forman and Argenti (2005) noted that the relationships between corporate communication and strategy implementation were visible because the organizations were going through obvious and significant strategic shifts. For instance, they noted that the companies they had investigated were interested in making sure that internal communication was felt and that information technology was at the heart of assuring plan implementation and reputation-building. The literature on strategy implementation, according to Vries (2014), indicates that there are five common challenges that businesses have while implementing strategies generally. Vries (2014) discovered and validated that there are at least 7 impediments to strategy implementation at the local authorities. The study also discovered that different respondents'/participants' perceptions of the barriers to strategy implementation have varying effects on the approach, with some having a big influence, others a moderate impact, and the remaining having a modest impact in the case of Council of Windhoek.

Additionally, Shopati *et al.*, (2018) identified 13 factors that are particularly effective at impeding the implementation of strategies, including non-accepting organizational cultures, divergent organizational cultures, unclear and ambiguous strategies, strategies that are not patient-centered, resource constraints, ineffective operational arrangements, a lack of commitment on the part of decision-makers, poor communication, disharmony, environmental uncertainty, a lack of clear leadership and guidance, and a lack of inspirational leaders. The examined research identifies the following barriers as being the most significant.

2.6 Chapter Summary

The researcher studied numerous academic works by other researchers on the subject of the factors influencing the adoption of strategic plans by local government bodies. The chapter has examined several theories, conceptual frameworks, and empirical evidence to pinpoint a knowledge gap.

3. Research methods

3.1 Introduction

The research design, target population, study sample (sample size), research tools, data collection techniques, data analysis, validity, reliability, and ethical issues were all covered in this chapter. The methods employed in this part will help the researcher better comprehend the effects of the Transformational Strategic Plan of the Windhoek Municipal Council (2017-2022).

3.2 Research Design

A descriptive research design was used during this study. According to Orodho (2002), descriptive research design is crucial for carrying out both exploratory and preliminary studies because it enables researchers to gather information, summarize it, and analyse it with the goal of making it clearer. A descriptive case study design framework was used in conjunction with qualitative method to achieve this goal.

3.3 Target Population

Windhoek Municipal Council employs about 2573 staff members in all departments. However, this study focused on a population of municipal and or council officials and staff, particularly those at management level. A target population refers to all the individuals who make up a real or fictitious group of individuals, occasions, or things to which a researcher desires to apply the findings of the research study (Borg & Gall 1989). The target group was sufficient because it included all components of the Municipal Council's Strategic Implementation Plan.

3.4 Sample

The target sample size for this study was 30 respondents from the Municipal Council of Windhoek (Municipal Council of Windhoek). The sample targeted mostly employees in senior and managerial positions and councilors due to their extensive involvement in the formulation of the strategic plan. The sample consisted of both male and female employees and covered all ages. Sample size is an important feature of any empirical study in which the goal is to make inferences about a population from a sample (According to Saunders, 2012). The target group for this study consisted of personnel at the top, middle, and supervisory levels of the Municipal Council of Windhoek who are directly involved in putting strategy into action. Because they develop the action plans that specify the steps necessary to address each of the major organizational challenges, how to achieve each of the relevant goals, who will carry out each step and when, top-level managers were important participants in the study. Middle level managers were particularly important study participants since they are implementation managers and as such, have the responsibility of developing, managing, and sustaining implementation in the councils. They are the council's most powerful members and have a significant impact on how its ethical and power structures are established and developed. On the other hand, supervisory level employees were helpful for this study because they will be affected if the council has an implementation problem, either directly or indirectly. Additionally, they are in charge of daily operations. A stratified random sample procedure was utilized in the study to choose participants from the top, middle, and supervisory personnel.

3.5 Research instruments

The research utilized a thorough semi structured questionnaire, which was designed and tested prior to the commencement of the official investigation. The planned questionnaires were administered in two portions, with both items directly addressing

the six questions that the proposed study has answered. Question 1 to 6 elicited information on the challenges that are impeding the successful implementation of the Transformational Strategic Plan 2017-2022, factors/ drivers of successful strategic implementation, stumbling blocks that must be overcome to achieve the goals and objectives set forth in the New strategic plan, and to assess the resource implications of the Transformational Strategic Plan 2017-2022 implementation.

3.6 Data collection procedure

The present study used the philosophy of pragmatics that focuses on human inquiry with a purpose. As problems arise and are acknowledged, inquiry is seen as a never-ending process that acknowledges the qualitative aspect of human experience. Recognition entails the uncertainty brought on by challenging ingrained belief structures. Through critical thinking and practical application, doubt is ultimately dispelled. With roots in the writings of Peirce (1984), James (1907), and Dewey (1931), as well as more recent backing from Rorty (1991), pragmatism emphasizes the real-world issues that individuals face, the suggested research questions, and the outcomes of that inquiry. With roots in the writings of Peirce (1984) and James (1907), pragmatism is a philosophy of knowledge building that places an emphasis on real-world answers to applied research questions as well as the outcomes of inquiry. It has been recommended by Brustad (2002) and others (Biddle, Markland, Gilbourne, Chatzisarantis, & Sparkes, 2001; Dewar & Horn, 1992) that researchers adopt a variety of approaches and embrace diverse perspectives. It is possible to apply multi-method techniques to solve any research subject, according to Brustad (2002), while Hardy *et al.*, (1996) provided the following: Sometimes using qualitative methods is best, and other times using a quantitative approach. Because both techniques have advantages and disadvantages, combining the two strategies may at times be beneficial (p. 259). In line with these ideas, it is crucial to keep discussing paradigms and epistemology in order to progress the application of mixed-method knowledge production in factors affecting implementation strategic plan. Questionnaires were used to collect data for the present study. Gay (1992) emphasized that questionnaires give respondents an opportunity of expressing views and offer suggestions. Because it provided respondents room and freedom to fill them out, the questionnaire tool was more valuable because some respondents could not be reached in time. Electronic mail was used to administer the questionnaires and to send them. Both quantitative and qualitative questionnaires detailing the research strategy and how the participants' views impacted the findings and conclusions were given to respondents. The Windhoek Municipal Council's senior and middle managers, as well as its members, were all randomly given questionnaires. In the interest of efficiency, the researcher evaluated the feedback from participants.

3.8 Validity and Reliability

This study used Cronbach's alpha to test for reliability of the responses. The reliability of data was achieved if the Cronbach's alpha is greater than 0.700 following Albdour & Altaraweh,

(2014). Furthermore, content validity was ensured through the research design by covering all departments and critical factors that affects the implementation of strategic plan from literature. Validity is the degree to which study findings accurately reflect what is going on in the scenario (Carter, Clegg & Kornberger, 2010). Considering answers to the items in the questionnaire, this study employed a Likert scale. Participants were provided a range of suggestions to choose from the one that perfectly represents their responses.

3.9 Research Ethics

The research has sought consent from both the Council and Chief Executive Officer, as well as organizational participants to ensure their information is treated confidentially. The researcher respected the confidentiality and anonymity of the research respondents by giving them assurance that their responses will only be used for academic purposes. The researcher ensured voluntarily participate of participants in the research.

3.10 Chapter summary

A research approach offers the study credibility and yields reliable scientific results. Additionally, it offers a thorough plan that aids in keeping researchers on course, facilitating a simple, efficient, and manageable approach. The research design, target population, study sample (sample size), research tools, data collection techniques, data analysis, validity, reliability, and ethical issues were all covered in this chapter. The methods employed in this part will help the researcher better comprehend the effects of the Transformational Strategic Plan of the Windhoek Municipal Council (2017-2022).

4. Data presentation, analysis and discussion findings

4.0 Introduction

In this chapter, findings on an analysis of the factors affecting the implementation of the municipal council of Windhoek's 2017-2022 transformational strategic plan were presented and discussed. The order of this chapter follows the objectives of this study. The chapter begins with the introduction in section 4.0, then described the sample number and reliability test results in section 4.1, followed by respondents' biographical information in section 4.2. Section 4.3 is the analysis of data and results which present results of the sub-objectives of this study in the chronological order. The results were then discussed in section 4.4 while the chapter ends with a summary of the chapter in section 4.5.

4.1 Sample number and reliability test results

The present study collected data through a self-administered questionnaire from the Municipal Council of Windhoek employees. Twenty-four responses were received out of 30 targeted representing a 77 % response rate. The reliability of respondents' scores on the variables that had more than one statement was determined using Cronbach's alpha (α) (Table 4.1). All variables were found to be within the acceptable range of > 0.700 (Albdour & Altaraweh, 2014), with current leadership (council & senior management) scoring the highest Cronbach's

alpha ($= 0.751$, $N = 7$) from the individual variables. The Cronbach's alpha was not computed for five variables (organizational culture, organizational design, resources, communication, and incentives) because they only had one statement each. However, when the reliability test was run on all statements for the current status and importance of the strategic plan, the α (0.816 , $N= 15$; 0.820 , $N= 15$, respectively) was within the acceptable limits.

Table 4.1: Reliability test results

Variable		Cronbach's alpha (α)	Number of statements (N)
Strategy formulation	Current	0.734	7
	Importance	0.724	7
Leadership (council & senior management)	Current	0.737	3
	Importance	0.751	3
Organisational culture	Current	N/A	1
	Importance	N/A	1
Organisational design	Current	N/A	1
	Importance	N/A	1
Resources	Current	N/A	1
	Importance	N/A	1
Communication	Current	N/A	1
	Importance	N/A	1
Incentives	Current	N/A	1
	Importance	N/A	1
All variables	Current	0.816	15
	Importance	0.820	15

4.2 Respondents' biographical information

Eight variables were used to describe the respondent's biographical information from the sampled population (section 4.2.1 – 4.2.7).

4.2.1 Gender

In terms of gender, the results showed that males made up the majority (72.22%) of the total 23 respondents in the survey. Females had the lowest representation (27.78%) (Fig. 4.1).

Figure 4.1: Information on respondents' gender.

Age group

In terms of age groups, the majority of respondents (60.87%) were from the age group 41-50, followed by the age group 31-40 (17.39%). The age group 20-30 had the least representation with 8.70 % (Fig. 4.2).

Figure 4.2: Information on respondents age group

4.2.3 Educational background

The majority of respondents (52.17%) had a bachelor's degree as their highest academic qualification. Holders of master's and doctorate degrees were the second most represented in terms of educational background (34.78%). Holders of other undefined academic qualifications had the lowest proportion (4.35%), followed by those with diplomas or advanced diplomas (8.70%) (Fig. 3).

Figure 4.3: Information on respondents' educational background.

4.2.4 Managerial training

Respondents were asked to specify which managerial in-service training they received while working for the Municipal Council of Windhoek. According to the findings, the majority of respondents (36.36%) received senior management training, followed by middle management training (22.73%), and executive management training (18.18%) (Fig. 4.4).

Furthermore, 9.09% of respondents had no training, while 13.64% had unidentified training (Fig. 4.4).

Figure 4.4: Information on respondents' in-service training.

4.2.5 Work department

In terms of work department, seven departments were represented, with the majority of respondents (26.32%) coming from the office of the chief executive officer, followed by respondents from the Department of capital and corporate services (21.05%) (Fig. 4.5). The department of economic development and community services, as well as the department of finance and customer services, had the third highest representation (15.79%) (Fig. 4.5). With 5.26% each, respondents from the department of electricity and city councillors had the lowest representation (Fig. 4.5).

Figure 4.5: Information on respondents' work department.

4.2.6 Employment core function

In terms of employee core functions, there were five core functions represented at the Municipal Council of Windhoek, with the majority of respondents (60.87%) from middle management and head of divisions, followed by executive officers and strategic executives (17.39%) representing the total samples (Fig. 4.5). Specialists and other unspecified core

functions were the third most represented (8.70%), while councillors were the least represented (4.35% of the total 23 respondents) (Fig. 4.6).

Figure 4.6: Information on respondents' core function.

4.2.7 Work experience

In terms of work experience, the majority of respondents (68.18%) have been with the company for at least 16 years, followed by those with 6-10 years of service. Respondents with at least 5 and 11-15 years of service (9.09%) had the lowest representation (Fig. 4.7).

Figure 4.7: Information on respondents' length of service at the organization

4.3 Analysis of data and results

This study used a self-administered questionnaire to collect data, which was then used to answer the research questions. The questionnaire had seven sections for quantitative data (strategic formulation, leadership, organizational culture, organizational design, resources, communication, and incentives) and six questions for qualitative data. Statements on the current status of the Municipal Council of Windhoek 2017-2022 strategic plan were rated on a five-point Likert-scale ranging from "no extent" to "very large extent," and statements on the importance of the 2017-2022 were rated from "not" to "critical." Descriptive

statistics analysis (mean and standard deviation) was used for the quantitative data while thematic analysis was used to summarise qualitative data. Sections 4.3.1 to 4.3.4 present the results following the objectives of the study.

4.3.1 Results for evaluation of the implementation of transformational strategic plan (2017-2022) for the Municipal Council of Windhoek.

The implementation of the transformational strategic plan for the period 2017 to 2022 for Municipal Council of Windhoek was evaluated based on items grouped in seven factors; strategy formulation, council and senior management leadership, organizational culture and design, resources, communication and incentives. These factors were evaluated based on the current status and the importance of the strategic plan.

4.3.1.1 Effect of strategic formulation

On the strategic formulation, results indicated that the item; to what extent are our strategic focus areas (KPAs) still relevant? had the highest mean score for the current status of the 2017-2022 strategic plan (M = 3.67, S.D. = 0.86) (Table 4.2). The second highest scored item for current status was; to indicate the

extent to which our KPIs are still effective for measuring progress towards our Objectives. (M = 3.32, S.D. = 0.78). The least scored item on the effect of strategic formulation was; indicated the extent to which the Objectives are no longer needed (M = 2.00, S.D. = 0.67) followed by, indicating the extent to which the objectives were met for the 2017-2022 strategic period (M = 2.59, S.D. = 0.59) (Table 4.2). In terms of the importance of the strategic formulation on the 2017-2022 strategic plan, results indicated that the items; indicate the extent of progress made towards reaching our vision (for the strategic period 2017-2022) and to what extent are our KPAs still relevant, had the highest mean score (M = 4.00, S.D. = 0.62, 0.53) (Table 4.2). The second highest scored item for the importance of strategic formulation was; to indicate the extent to which the targets set, were realistic (M = 3.91, S.D. = 0.61). The least scored item on the importance strategic formulation was; indicated the extent to which the objectives are no longer needed (M = 3.35, S.D. = 0.90) followed by, indicate the extent to which the objectives were met for the 2017-2022 strategic period (M = 3.81, S.D. = 0.93) (Table 4.2).

Table 4.2: Descriptive statistics results for the effect of strategy formulation on the current and importance of the transformational strategic plan (2017-2022).

Item	Current status					Importance				
	N	Min.	Max.	Mean	SD	N	Min.	Max.	Mean	SD
Indicate the extent of progress made towards reaching our Vision (for the strategic period 2017-2022)	22	1.00	5.00	2.77	0.81	22	3.00	5.00	4.00	0.62
To what extent are our Strategic Focus Areas (KPAs) still relevant?	21	1.00	5.00	3.67	0.86	22	3.00	5.00	4.00	0.53
Indicate the extent to which the Objectives were met for the 2017-2022 strategic period	22	1.00	3.00	2.59	0.59	21	2.00	5.00	3.81	0.93
Indicate the extent to which the Objectives are no longer needed	22	1.00	3.00	2.00	0.62	20	2.00	5.00	3.35	0.90
Indicate the extent to which the Projects/initiatives required to deliver incomplete Objectives, are sufficient	21	2.00	5.00	3.10	0.83	22	2.00	5.00	3.82	0.80
Indicate the extent to which our KPIs are still effective for measuring progress towards our Objectives.	22	2.00	5.00	3.32	0.78	22	2.00	5.00	3.82	0.80
Indicate the extent to which the targets set, were realistic	22	1.00	4.00	2.82	0.80	22	3.00	5.00	3.91	0.61

4.3.1.2 Effect of council and senior management leadership

On the effect of council and senior management leadership on the current and importance of the transformational strategic plan (2017-2022) three items were measured on based on a five-point Likert-scale ranging from "no extent" to "very large extent," for items on current status and from "not" to "critical" for items on importance. Results indicated that the item; indicate the extent to which the current leadership development programmes, are effective, had the highest mean score for current status of the 2017-2022 strategic plan (M = 2.91, S.D. = 1.08) (Table 4.3). The second highest scored item for current status was; indicate the extent to which the performance management system/process was implemented (monitoring, evaluation & reporting) (M = 2.83, S.D. = 0.98). The least scored item on the effect of strategic formulation was; indicate the extent to which the current leadership attraction & retention strategies, are effective (M = 2.78, S.D. = 0.95) (Table 4.3).

In terms of the importance of the council and senior management leadership, results indicated that the item; which indicate the extent to which the performance management system/process was implemented (monitoring, evaluation & reporting), had the highest mean score (M = 4.13, S.D. = 0.69) (Table 4.3). The second highest scored item for the importance of council and senior management leadership was; to indicate the extent to which the current leadership attraction & retention strategies, are effective (M = 4.09, S.D. = 0.85). The least scored item was; indicate the extent to which the current leadership development programmes, are effective (M = 3.91, S.D. = 0.90) (Table 4.3).

Items	Current status					Importance				
	N	Min.	Max.	Avg.	Std. Dev.	N	Min.	Max.	Avg.	Std. Dev.
Indicate the extent to which the current leadership attraction & retention strategies, are effective	23	1.00	4.00	2.78	0.95	23	2.00	5.00	4.09	0.85
Indicate the extent to which the current leadership development programmes are effective	23	1.00	4.00	2.91	1.08	23	2.00	5.00	3.91	0.90
Indicate the extent to which the performance management system/process was implemented (monitoring, evaluation & reporting)	23	2.00	5.00	2.83	0.98	23	3.00	5.00	4.13	0.69

Table 4.3: Descriptive statistics results for the effect of council and senior management leadership on the current and importance of the transformational strategic plan (2017-2022).

4.3.1.3 Effect organizational culture, organizational design, resources, communication, and incentives.

On the effect of organizational culture, organizational design, resources, communication, and incentives on the current and importance of the transformational strategic plan (2017-2022) one item was measured for each factor. A five-point Likert-scale was used ranging from "no extent" to "very large extent," for items on current status and from "not" to "critical" for items on importance. Results indicated that on the organizational culture, the item; indicate the extent to which the organisational culture fosters the organisational values received a mean score of 2.87 (S.D. = 1.36) for current status of the 2017-2022 strategic plan. This item received a mean score of 4.26 (S.D. = 0.81) on the importance scale (Table 4.4). In terms of the organizational design, the item; Indicate the extent to which the strategy was structured towards smooth implementation (e.g. organisational structure, systems, processes) received a mean score of 3.13 (S.D. = 0.92) for current status of the 2017-2022 strategic plan.

This item received a mean score of 4.13 (S.D. = 0.55) on the importance scale (Table 4.4). With regards to the effect of resources, the item; indicate the extent to which the strategy was financially resourced (e.g. organisational structure, systems, processes) received a mean score of 2.30 (S.D. = 0.93) for current status of the 2017-2022 strategic plan. This item received a mean score of 4.26 (S.D. = 0.62) on the importance scale (Table 4.4). On the effect of communication, the item; indicate the extent to which the strategy was communicated and regularly promoted received a mean score of 2.30 (S.D. = 0.93) for current status of the 2017-2022 strategic plan. This item received a mean score of 4.26 (S.D. = 0.62) on the importance scale (Table 4.4). On the effect of incentives, the item; indicate the extent to which incentives were awarded for good performance received a mean score of 1.22 (S.D. = 0.52) for current status of the 2017-2022 strategic plan. This item received a mean score of 3.87 (S.D. = 1.01) on the importance scale (Table 4.4).

Table 4.4: Descriptive statistics results for the effect of organizational culture and design, resources, communication and incentives on the current and importance of the transformational strategic plan (2017-2022).

Statement	Current status					Importance				
	N	Min.	Max.	Avg.	Std. Dev.	N	Min.	Max.	Avg.	Std. Dev.
Organizational culture										
Indicate the extent to which the organisational culture fosters the organisational values	23	1.00	5.00	2.87	1.36	23	2.00	5.00	4.26	0.81
Organizational design										
Indicate the extent to which the strategy was structured towards smooth implementation (e.g. organisational structure, systems, processes)	23	2.00	5.00	3.13	0.92	23	3.00	5.00	4.13	0.55
Resources										
Indicate the extent to which the strategy was financially resourced	23	1.00	4.00	2.30	0.93	23	3.00	5.00	4.26	0.62
Communication										
Indicate the extent to which the strategy was communicated and regularly promoted	23	1.00	5.00	3.09	1.04	23	3.00	5.00	4.30	0.56
Incentives										
Indicate the extent to which incentives were awarded for good performance	23	1.00	3.00	1.22	0.52	23	1.00	5.00	3.87	1.01

4.3.1.4 Overall scores

Overall, scores for the organizational design had the highest mean of 3.13 (S.D. = 0.92) for current status of the 2017-2022 strategic plan followed by scores on communication (M = 3.09, S.D. = 1.04). The least scored factor was incentives (M = 1.22, S.D. = 0.52) followed by scores for resources (M = 2.3, S.D. = 0.93) and current status of the 2017-2022 strategic plan (Table 4.5).

In terms of the importance of these factors on the implementation of the 2017-2022 strategic plan, scores for communication had the highest mean of 4.30 (S.D. = 0.56) followed by organizational culture and resources with both scoring mean of 4.26. The least scored factor was incentives (M = 3.87, S.D. = 1.01) followed by strategy formulation (M = 3.87, S.D. = 1.01) (Table 4.5).

Table 4.5: Descriptive statistics results for overall scores of the effect of seven factors that were evaluated on the current and importance of the transformational strategic plan (2017-2022).

Item	Current status					Importance				
	N	Min.	Max.	Mean	Std. Dev.	N	Min.	Max.	Mean	Std. Dev.
Strategy formulation	22	2.00	3.86	2.89	0.47	22	2.71	4.57	3.83	0.46
Leadership (council & senior management)	23	1.33	4.00	2.84	0.82	23	2.33	5.00	4.04	0.67
Organisational culture	23	1.00	5.00	2.87	1.36	23	2.00	5.00	4.26	0.81
Organisational design	23	2.00	5.00	3.13	0.92	23	3.00	5.00	4.13	0.55
Resources	23	1.00	4.00	2.30	0.93	23	3.00	5.00	4.26	0.62
Communication	23	1.00	5.00	3.09	1.04	23	3.00	5.00	4.30	0.56
Incentives	23	1.00	3.00	1.22	0.52	23	1.00	5.00	3.87	1.01

A five-point Likert scale with cut off points adapted from Albdour and Altaraweh was used to determine the level of responses (2014). Therefore, the mean scores of all variables were divided into three categories: low (M = 2.00), moderate (M = 2.00 - 3.50), and high (M = > 3.5). The results indicate that the effect of strategy formulation on current status of the 2017 – 2022 Municipal Council of Windhoek strategic plan was moderate (M = 2.89, SD = 0.47) while for importance of the strategy formulation on the strategic plan was high (M = 3.83, SD = 0.46). The effect of council and senior management leadership was also moderate for current status of the strategic plan (M = 2.84, SD = 0.82) while for the importance it was high (M = 4.04, SD = 0.67). Similarly, the effect of organisational culture, organizational design, resources and communication were all found to be moderate for current status of the 2017 – 2022 strategic plan with mean scores of 2.87 (S.D = 1.36), 3.13 (S.D = 0.92), 2.30 (S.D = 0.93) and 3.09 (S.D = 1.04) respectively. In addition, all these factors were found to be of high importance (M = 4.26, S.D = 0.81; M = 4.13, S.D. = 0.55, M = 4.26, S.D. = 0.62 and M = 4.30, S.D. = 0.56 respectively). The effect of incentives on the current status of the strategic plan was found to be low (M = 1.22, S.D = 0.52) while the importance of incentives was found to be high (M = 3.87, S.D. = 1.01).

indicated that the importance of the considered factors on the implementation of the 2017-2022 strategic plan had higher score than that of current status. The results also indicated that overall, scores for organizational design had the highest mean of 3.13 (S.D. = 0.92) for current status of the 2017-2022 strategic plan while scores for communication had the highest mean of 4.30 (S.D. = 0.56) for the importance of the strategic plan. Furthermore, results indicated that the least scored factor for the current status and importance was incentives (M = 1.22, S.D. = 0.52 and M = 3.87, S.D. = 1.01, respectively). Apart from incentives, all other factors were found to be of moderate effect on the current status of the 2017 – 2022 strategic plan. Furthermore, all seven factors were found to be of high importance to the implementation of the 2017 – 2022 strategic plan for Municipal Council of Windhoek.

4.3.1.5 Summary for research objective one

The transformational strategic plan for Municipal Council of Windhoek from 2017 to 2022 was evaluated based on seven factors: strategy formulation, council and senior management leadership, organizational culture and design, resources, communication, and incentives. A five-point Likert-scale was used to score items for all factors on a scale ranging from "no extent" to "very large extent," for items on current status and from "not" to "critical" for items on importance. Results

4.3.2 Results for identification of the challenges that affected the implementation of the transformational strategic plan (2017-2022) for Municipal Council of Windhoek.

Employees of the Municipal Council of Windhoek were asked to identify challenges that have affected the implementation of the transformational strategic plan (2017 – 2022) through a self-administered questionnaire. The data was analysed thematically where similar sounding statement were given the same coded label and their frequency of occurrence in all responses was determined. Sixteen challenges were identified with lack of funds being the most frequent (22 %, n = 11) followed by administration issues and leadership vacuum, both with 12 % (n = 6) of the total frequencies (Table 4.6). The least frequent challenges were; lack of consistency in decision-making, internal bureaucratic process, lack of planning, lack of central government support, lack of performance incentives and external factors, all with 2 % (n = 1) (Table 4.6).

Table 4.6: Challenges that have affected the implementation of the Municipal Council of Windhoek 2017 -2022 transformational strategic plan.

Challenges	Frequency (n)	Percentages (%)
Leadership vacuum	6	12
Lack of corporation from stakeholders	2	4
Lack of funds	11	22
Lack of consistency in decision-making	1	2
Internal bureaucratic process	1	2
Political interference	4	8
Lack of planning	1	2
Administration issues	6	12
Lack of central government support	1	2
Limited expertise	5	10
Lack of performance incentives	1	2
Covid-19	2	4
External factors	1	2
Over ambitious targets	3	6
Lack of accountability	3	6
Communication barrier	2	4

4.3.2.1 Summary for Objective Two

Using a self-administered questionnaire, the challenges affecting Municipal Council of Windhoek 's transformational strategic plan from 2017 to 2022 were identified. The data was analyzed using a thematic analysis method. Sixteen challenges were identified, with lack of funds being the most frequent (22%, n = 11), followed by administration issues and a leadership vacuum, both of which accounted for 12% (n = 6) of the total frequencies. With 2% (n = 1), the least frequent challenges were lack of consistency in decision-making, internal bureaucratic process, lack of planning, lack of central government support, lack of performance incentives, and external factors.

4.3.3 Results for examination and outline of the critical success factors of the strategic plan (2017-2022) implementation.

Through a self-administered questionnaire, Municipal Council of Windhoek employees were asked to outline success factors for the implementation of the transformational strategic plan (2017-2022). The data was analysed thematically, with similar sounding statements given the same coded label and their frequency of occurrence determined in all responses. Eighteen success factors were identified, with the most common financial resources (19.70 %, n = 13), followed by support of council and senior management leadership (12%, n = 6) (Table 4.7). Support from central government and accountability were the least frequent success factors, each with 1.52 % (n = 1) of the total responses followed by good administration strategies, stakeholder involvement, clear strategies, organizational structure, training and political will (3.03 %, n = 2) (Table 4.7).

Table 4.7: Success factors for implementing the Municipal Council of Windhoek 2017 -2022 transformational strategic plan.

Factors	Frequency	Percentages (%)
Support of council and senior management leadership	8	12.12
Political will	2	3.03
Human resources	6	9.09
Monitoring and evaluation of projects	4	6.06
Financial resources	13	19.70
Employees Incentives	3	4.55
Achievable goals	4	6.06
Teamwork	3	4.55
Organisational structure	2	3.03
Clear strategies	2	3.03
Stakeholders' involvement	2	3.03
Effective communication	3	4.55
Training	2	3.03
Support from central government	1	1.52
Implementation action plan	3	4.55
Accountability	1	1.52
Good administration strategies	2	3.03
Implementation of performance management system	5	7.58

4.3.3.1 Summary for objective three

City of Windhoek employees were asked to outline success factors for the transformational strategic plan's implementation via a self-administered questionnaire (2017-2022). Eighteen

success factors were identified, with financial resources being the most common (19.70%, n = 13), followed by council and senior management leadership support (12%, n = 6). The least

frequent success factors were central government support and accountability, each with 1.52% (n = 1).

4.4 Discussion of findings

The current study's findings were thoroughly discussed by comparing and contrasting them with the findings of previous related studies focusing on the study's objectives.

4.4.1 To evaluate how the Municipal Council of Windhoek implemented its transformational strategic plan (2017-2022).

The evaluation of the implementation of the Municipal Council of Windhoek 2017-2022 transformational strategic plan revealed that the importance of the factors considered on the implementation of the 2017-2022 strategic plan had a higher score than the current status. Overall, scores for organizational design had the highest mean for the current status of the 2017-2022 strategic plan, while scores for communication had the highest mean for the strategic plan's importance. The results of this study are in line with research done by Hill and Jones (2013), who emphasized that an organization's culture has a direct or indirect impact on its efficiency and effectiveness. Hill and Jones (2013) further argued that it is important to have a culture that values dedication, efficiency, effectiveness, and openness. Member self-image, inner workings, relationships with the outside world as well as the expectations for the future are attributes of an organizational culture (Needle, 2004). Considering the high score of organization design, this is an indication that Municipal Council of Windhoek is currently practicing all the attributes of that can drive a successful implementation of a strategic plan. The respondents strongly deliberate that communication within the organization plays a critical role in the implementation of strategic plans. For the reason that it promotes the exchange of information, ideas, beliefs, perceptions, advice, opinions, commands, and instructions, internal it permits information flow, but the pertinent data must go continually from top to bottom and vice versa (Daniel, 2019).

By communicating with one another, managers, employees, and other staff members cultivate positive interpersonal relationships. Ahoy (2011) emphasized that strategic plans can successfully be implemented if top executives communicate it to the whole organization for implementation purposes. Furthermore, incentives were the least scored factor for current status and importance (M = 1.22, S.D. = 0.52 and M = 3.87, S.D. = 1.01, respectively). All seven factors, excluding incentives, were found to have a moderate impact on the strategic plan's current state from 2017 to 2022. Furthermore, all factors were found to be of high important for the Municipal Council of Windhoek strategic plan's implementation from 2017 to 2022. Surprisingly, Municipal Council of Windhoek considers incentives to have the lowest effect on its strategic plan's implementation for 2017-2022. This is contrary to Kennedy (2000) findings, who reported that incentives have a significant impact on culture. By incentives, we refer to the complete range of rewards, including monetary rewards, non-monetary benefits

like status, recognition, and advancement, and sanctions that members of the organization are subject to.

4.4.2 To identify the challenges that affected the implementation of the transformational strategic plan (2017-2022) for the Municipal Council of Windhoek.

The challenges affecting the Municipal Council of Windhoek 's transformational strategic plan from 2017 to 2022 were identified using a self-administered questionnaire. Sixteen challenges were identified, with the most common being a lack of funds followed by administration issues and a leadership vacuum. The least common challenges were a lack of consistency in decision-making, an internal bureaucratic process, a lack of planning, a lack of central government support, a lack of performance incentives, and external factors.

Buluma *et.al* (2013) also noted the same challenges and factors as the present study that influence the implementation of the strategic plan. The effects of institutional-related factors affecting the implementation of strategic plans, such as inadequate technological resources, insufficient management systems, the council lacked control over the implementation of strategic plans, insufficient management approaches, and inadequate support from the central government towards the implementation of the council's strategic plan.

The findings concur with Olivier and Schwella (2018), who discovered that obstacles to effective implementation can be broken down into seven categories: poor leadership, the strategic plan itself, poor project management, poor alignment of the strategy with the rest of the organization, a lack of a proper strategy execution or performance management system (PMS), poor motivation, and poor engagement.

Additionally, Shopati *et al.*, (2018) identified 13 factors that are particularly effective at impeding the implementation of strategies, including non-accepting organizational cultures, divergent organizational cultures, unclear and ambiguous strategies, strategies that are not patient-centered, resource constraints, ineffective operational arrangements, a lack of commitment on the part of decision-makers, poor communication, disharmony, environmental uncertainty, a lack of clear leadership and guidance, and a lack of inspirational leaders. The examined research identifies the following barriers as being the most significant. Other obstacles do exist, it must be said. According to research by Salum *et al.*, (2017), among the reasons why public organizations struggle to implement strategic plans is the issue with poor strategic plan design, poor resource management and monitoring and assessment are further contributing issues. However, the failure of leaders to manage and inspire their teams to achieve the goals of the strategic plan is criticized.

4.4.3 To examine and outline the critical success factors of the strategic plan implementation.

Employees of the City of Windhoek were asked to outline success factors for the transformational strategic plan's implementation via a self-administered questionnaire (2017-2022). Eighteen challenges were identified, with financial

resources being the most common followed by council and senior management leadership support. Central government support and accountability were the least common success factors. Financial resources are one of the common methods of evaluating resources, which is according to this study is one of the main challenges identified in the implementation of the City of Windhoek (2017-2022) strategic plans implementation. Daniel (2019) highlighted that the scope of the project you're working on must be determined prior the allocation of resources, taking the time frame of the project into consideration. Successful implementation of any strategic plan is a dead end in the absence of sufficient of financial resources (Mumbua and Mingaine, 2015). The findings from this study also indicated that council and senior management support were lacking, which is a big concern because management support is considered an important role in strategy plan implementation (Mumbua and Mingaine, 2015). It's common to think that middle managers' support or opposition of strategy change is primarily motivated by their own personal interests in the strictest sense of the word (e.g., gains or losses in their organizational status, role, or economic incentives) (Huy, 2011). Leaders continue to play a crucial role in the execution or implementation of strategies. This is due to the fact that strategy execution focuses on putting the plan into practice, or more simply expressed, making it a reality. Kubica and White (2007) state that middle managers offer value to organizations that are executing strategies in the public sector. According to Freed and Currie, middle managers should play a different role because they are seen as nothing more than bureaucrats who serve as obstacles to change rather than adding much value to the execution of strategies. Katoma and Ungerer (2011) reported that some middle managers in some cases, do indeed play roles that detract from the value of the organization by acting in disruptive ways, such as working on personal projects during business hours, adopting a laissez-faire attitude, and being preoccupied with routine operational tasks that belong at lower levels. On the contrary the present finding is different from that of Yang *et al.*, (2010) whose research showed that the involvement and interventions of an organization's highest level of management foster greater commitment levels in the implementation of a firm's vision and strategies, which in turn fosters success in the implementation of a firm's chosen strategy. Smith and Kofron (1996), however, thought that the senior management played a significant role in the formulation and implementation of the strategy than all other factors.

4.5 Chapter summary

The goal of this study was to assess the effectiveness of the transformational strategic plan for the period 2017-2022, as well as to identify implementation challenges that the Municipal Council of Windhoek faced. The quantitative data was analysed using descriptive statistics, while the qualitative data was analysed using thematic analysis. The results indicated that all factors considered for this study were of high importance in terms of the implementation of the Municipal Council of Windhoek 2017 – 2022 transformational strategic plan. The effect of the considered factors was of moderate effect on the

implementation of the strategic plan. Various challenges and success factors including financial resources and administration issues were identified for implementation of the strategic plan.

5. Summary, conclusion and recommendations

5.1 Summary

This study perused four specific objectives in order to analyse factors affecting the implementation of the Municipal Council of Windhoek (Municipal Council of Windhoek) 2017 – 2022 transformational strategic plan. The data were collected from the Municipal Council of Windhoek employees through a self-administered questionnaire. Data were summarized using descriptive statistics and thematic analyses methods. The current study's findings were thoroughly discussed by comparing and contrasting them with the findings of previous related studies focusing on the study's objectives. On the evaluation of the implementation of the Municipal Council of Windhoek 2017-2022 transformational strategic plan, seven factors were used; strategic formulation, council and senior management leadership, organizational culture, organizational design, resources, communication and incentives. All seven factors, excluding incentives, were found to have a moderate impact on the strategic plan's current state from 2017 to 2022. Furthermore, all factors were found to be of high importance for the Municipal Council of Windhoek strategic plan's implementation from 2017 to 2022. On the challenges affecting Municipal Council of Windhoek 's transformational strategic plan, sixteen challenges were identified, with the most common being a lack of funds followed by administration issues and a leadership vacuum. The least common challenges were a lack of consistency in decision-making, an internal bureaucratic process, a lack of planning, a lack of central government support, a lack of performance incentives, and external factors. On the success factors for the transformational strategic plan's implementation, eighteen challenges were identified, with financial resources being the most common followed by council and senior management leadership support. Central government support and accountability were the least common success factors. The implications of these findings are that all variables were found to be of high importance in terms of the strategy implementation. However, most of the variables were of moderate effect in terms of the current status. This imply that even though the implementation was a success, there is still a lot to be improved for future strategic plans as various challenges were identified.

5.2 CONCLUSION

There are various factors that affect implementation of strategic plans in literature. However, based on the finding of this study titled: an analysis of the factors affecting the implementation of the municipal council of Windhoek's 2017-2022 transformational strategic plan, the present study suggested that effect of; strategic formulation, council and senior management leadership, organizational culture, organizational design, resources, communication and incentives are all of high importance. Furthermore, the present study suggest that these factors were of moderate effect on the implementation of

strategic plans apart from incentives. With this, results it can be concluded that factors that are perceived to be of high importance to the implementation of the strategic plan do not always yield substantial results. In addition, various challenges and success drivers can influence success of the municipal strategic plan implementation notably funds and effective administration.

5.3 RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study the following recommendations were made to the Municipal Council of Windhoek (Municipal Council of Windhoek):

- Future strategic plan should have clear and achievable goals and implementation strategies.
- The Municipal Council of Windhoek should improve its financial resources for all project and activities in the strategic plan.
- The Municipal Council of Windhoek should improve its administration, particularly the council and senior management leadership in terms of collective support for implementation of future strategic plans.
- The Municipal Council of Windhoek should implement the performance management system in order to improve accountability of employees.
- The Municipal Council of Windhoek should improve its projects monitoring and evaluation process in order to improve effectiveness and efficiency of the implementation of strategic plans.
- Strategic plans periods should coincide with the term of the council.
- Leadership must assume responsibility for the procedure in order to guarantee compliance and adherence to all requirements for implementation and execution of the strategy
- Continuously staff engagement by providing them with training and reorientations is recommended.
- Municipal Council of Windhoek should commit to budget plan, quarterly evaluation and reporting for timely amendment.
- Improve communication by providing regular feedback to employees.

In addition, future studies can focus on conducting a comprehensive study aimed at finding best strategies for successful implementation of strategic plans in the Municipal Council of Windhoek. Future studies can also focus on other municipal towns in the country.

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